

JUSTICE OF IMAM AL-BUKHARI

Murodkhonov Mukhammad Sodiq

Student of Kokaldosh secondary special school under
the Muslim Board of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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Annotation: There are many examples and signs for today's generation in the way of life of Allah Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Ismail al-Bukhari, who has made an invaluable contribution to the development of the history and culture of our people, the religion of Islam and Hadith studies. As we enter the treasure of knowledge, which has become an invaluable wealth from our ancestors, we see that all the qualities necessary for the development of the personality society are embodied in the works of Imam Al-Bukhari. Especially today, which is attributed to us as the third period of awakening, the need for this spiritual heritage is great. In this article, opinions and comments will be made about the Justice of Imam Al Bukhari.

Keywords: Imam al Bukhari, Justice, hadiths, religious views, knowledge.

Imam Al-Bukhari lived every second of lifelong believe in the existence of an account before the Lord. Therefore, the person appreciated the time. Did not step in vain. The constantly awake heart of the teacher was disturbed by the anxiety of the nation, the grief of the Islamic Ummah. They worked very carefully to fulfill the great and honorable task entrusted to them without shortcomings. In the day-to-day tanovul, they paid serious attention to the Haram with honesty. Thanks to this, even suspicious things could not cast a shadow on the bite. The more perfect his prayer, his knowledge, his Justice in life, his humility, his generosity were so unequal. He inherited from his father a countless world to man. He would sew it to trade and multiply, and the profits received would be constantly donated to the widows, the needy. Imam Al-Bukhari had a lot of such qualities, which were the highest sign of human perfection. About one of them they write like this: "since I know that gossip is forbidden, I have not slandered a person."

He cites in his memoirs the person who made the man a secretary: "he would give the very great wealth left by his father to muzoraba (multiplied commercially on the basis of mutual partnership). The one who borrowed one trip did not return his twenty-five thousand. Some said to him:" it will be useful if you take the letter of the Governor." Then Imam Al-Bukhari said to them, " if I receive a letter from them, they will remain a taste of me. I will not sell my world, " they said. This is what he says in another memoir about the fact that a person is a Just person:

"They brought him the burden that Abu Hafs had given. In the evening, a group of merchants arrived and offered to make a profit of five thousand dirhams from this trade. Imam Al-Bukhari advised them to be patient and wait tonight.

The next day, other merchants agreed and offered ten thousand dirhams of profit for the goods. Then he said, "I intend to give it to those who came before you last night, I do not want to break my intention," and gave the goods to those who came first, even if five thousand dirhams were of little benefit."

"Often rode Mount, OG was lodged out of the horse. During the time I accompanied that person, I only saw twice that his arrows did not touch the target."

Standing in the Pharaoh, we went out on the road leading to the Harbor (port) and started the arrow father. One of the arrows fired from Imam Al-Bukhari's bow went to the bridge rope built on the water, and the rope broke. When he saw it, he fell off his mount and pulled out the arrow on his back. The arrow stopped shooting and said: "Come Back."

We went back. Then he turned to me and said, with a heavy breath, "o, Abu Ja'far, I need you." I expressed my interest in listening to him. It is:

"If you go to the owner of the bridge! We damaged the rope. We ask that you allow us to weigh someone else in his place or pay for the value and forgive us for what we did, "you said.

Since the owner of the bridge was a man named Humayd ibn Axzar, I searched for him. I delivered the deposit that was told to him. And he told me:

"Say hello to Abu Abdullah and say to him:" I have forgiven what you have done. Let all my property be sacrificed to you", -he said.

Abu Ja'far will deliver the said deposit to Imam Al-Bukhari in full. Then, his faces suddenly crack and a sign of joy appears on his face. Abu Ja'far said that on this day Imam Al-Bukhari read five hundred Hadiths and sent three hundred dirhams out of his property as charity."

Such qualities in the Sultan of mukhaddis are a lesson school for each of us in our days. To build a fair society, especially in the face of the transparent policy pursued by our esteemed President, these school lessons are necessary with water!

In the days when modesty and knowledge are required from governors, law enforcement agencies, heads of enterprises and organizations in the regions, he is a person's lifestyle, honesty code, resolute justice, perfect faith passenger Star. The book makes illiterate people suffer spiritual poverty. And a person without knowledge goes astray even in the daytime. Thanks to this, some leaders in our

society, the neighborhood elders, were subjected to the pain of bribery. Entrepreneurs assess the artificial increase in prices in the markets in the hope of making a big profit from trade simply as a necessity of living. In fact, what a great sin these are, is perfectly inscribed in the works of Imam Al-Bukhari.

Religious leaders — scribes, who must show diligence in eliminating the layer of poverty in our society (who have not yet passed away from the dry advice in the mosques), owe a lifetime to the genius of Imam Al-Bukhari. Because they cannot go even closer to the first step of the golden staircase, which in the world of spirituality and eternity was conquered by that person. The reason is that the qualities of perseverance, courage, sincerity, dedication in Imam Al-Bukhari are not visible in our something scribes.

After all, Imam Al-Bukhari was always a supporter of the oppressed, the needy, the stranger, the debtors, a keeper of justice between the lowest layer of society and the rulers. He respected scientists kneeling in the face of people called. Amiru rulers lived waiting for years for his visit to the kingdom, without hoping for the barracks of the prayers of that person. And Imam Al-Bukhari loved to live among the ordinary people, avoiding going to the palaces. The man built a rabot near Bukhara. The people who heard this, came down like a flood to help in this rewarding work. The leader of the mukhaddis did not suffice it, giving himself cannibalized the sleeve and transported it to the Masters.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. Insonparvarlik, ezgulik va bunyodkrlik – milliy g'oyamiz poydevoridir. – T.: “Tavsir” 2021-yil.
2. Ahmad Lutfiy Qozonchi. Xazrati Umar ibn Xattob roziyallohu anhu. – T.: “Movarounnahr” 2005-yil.
3. Abu Abdulloh Muhammad Ibn Ismoil Al-Buxoriy. Hadis, 1-jild. Al-Jome as-Sahih. – T.: 1991-yil.
4. Abu Nasr Kalaboziy. Rijolu Sahih al-Buxoriy. – B.: “Tag’liq” 2007-yil.
5. Abdusattor Shayx. Imom Buxoriy ustozil asotiziyn va imomil muhaddisiyn.... Damashq, “Dor al-qalam” 2007-yil.
6. Taqyid al-Muhammil. Tabaqot al-Hanobila. – B. : “Tag’liq” 2007-yil.

